

SULPHONAMIDES. PART II.

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Anilino-, toluidino-, anisidino-, phenetidino-, xyfidino-, 5-aminoquinolino-, anisidino-acetylamino-*p*-benzenesulphonamides and various allied products have been synthesised for studying their therapeutic activity and toxicity.

In Part I of this series of papers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 495) sulphonamides having quinoline ring in the molecule have been described. In the present investigation, sulphonamides of the type (I) and (II) have been synthesised.

where R = PhNH, EtO'C₆H₄NH, MeO'C₆H₄NH and Me'C₆H₄NH.

For this purpose, *p*-*o*-chloroacetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride was converted into the corresponding amide, which was then condensed with various amines to give the substances of the type (I). The substances of the type (II) were obtained by direct condensation of *p*-*o*-chloroacetaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride with two molecules of the bases.

The products will be tested for their therapeutic activity and toxicity when facilities are available.

EXPERIMENTAL.

o-Anilinoacetylamino-*p*-benzenesulphonamide (I, R = PhNH).—A solution of *p*-*o*-chloroacetylamino-*p*-benzenesulphonamide (2 g.) and aniline (2 mol., 1.5 c.c.) in absolute methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) was heated on a steam-bath for 14 hours. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue was crystallised from 33% alcohol, m.p. 196°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 13.75. C₁₂H₁₃O₂N₃S requires N, 13.77 per cent).

The compounds described below were prepared in the same manner as the aniline derivative.

ω-Diethylaminoacetylaminop-*p*-benzenesulphonamide (I, R = NEt₂) crystallised from water, m.p. 153°. (Found: N, 14.67. C₁₂H₁₆O₂N₂S requires N, 14.7 per cent).

ω-*o*-Anisidinoacetylaminobenzene-*p*-sulphonamide.— After distilling off the methyl alcohol, the residue was extracted with boiling water, which on cooling deposited a white solid, which after crystallisation from 98% alcohol had m.p. 189°. (Found: N, 12.34. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 12.53 per cent).

ω-*m*-Anisidinoacetylaminobenzene-*p*-sulphonamide crystallised from 50% methyl alcohol, m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 12.25; S, 9.6. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 12.53; S, 9.5 per cent).

ω-*p*-Anisidinoacetylaminobenzene-*p*-sulphonamide crystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, m.p. 189°. (Found: N, 12.8. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 12.53 per cent).

ω-*o*-Toluidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (I, R = Me·C₆H₄NH).— After distilling off the methyl alcohol, the semi-solid residue was triturated with water and filtered. The residue after crystallisation from alcohol separated as rhombic plates, m.p. 212°. (Found: N, 12.96. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 13.17 per cent).

ω-*m*-Toluidinoacetylaminobenzene-*p*-sulphonamide crystallised from 70% alcohol, m.p. 166°. (Found: N, 12.81. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 13.17 per cent).

ω-*p*-Toluidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 189°. (Found: N, 13.06. C₁₅H₁₇O₄N₂S requires N, 13.17 per cent).

ω-*o*-Phenetidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (I, R = OEt·C₆H₄NH).— A solution of *p*-*ω*-chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (1 mol., 2.5 g.) and *o*-phenetidine (2 mol., 2.7 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 14 hours. After cooling, the solvent was filtered off and the residue refluxed again with 40 c.c. of absolute methyl alcohol. It was then filtered hot and the insoluble residue was crystallised from dioxan in plates, m.p. 221°. (Found: N, 11.51. C₁₆H₁₉O₄N₂S requires N, 12.03 per cent).

ω-*m*-Phenetidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide.— After distillation of methyl alcohol, the residue was lixiviated with cold water and then crystallised from hot water. Finally it was crystallised from 98% alcohol and had m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 11.74. C₁₆H₁₉O₄N₂S requires N, 12.03 per cent).

ω-*p*-Phenetidinoacetylaminobenzene-*p*-sulphonamide.— After the separation of the solids were well washed with methyl alcohol and finally

crystallised from 98% alcohol, m.p. 209° (decomp.). (Found : N, 11'84 ; S, 9'1. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12'03 ; S, 8'4 per cent).

o-Xylidinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (I, R = $Me_2C_6H_3NH$).—The residue after distilling off methyl alcohol was triturated with cold water and filtered. The insoluble mass was then extracted with hot water several times. The hot water extracts, on cooling, deposited crystals, which on recrystallisation from 50% alcohol had m.p. 163°. (Found : N, 12'93. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12'61 per cent).

o-*p*-Aminoazobenzeneacetylbenzenesulphonamide (I, R = NHC_6H_4N : NPh)
—*p*-*o*-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (1 mol., 1'5 g.) and *p*-aminoazobenzene (2 mol., 2'3 g.) were dissolved in absolute methyl alcohol (40 c.c.), and the mixture heated at 100° for 10 hours. The separated solids were collected and washed thoroughly with absolute methyl alcohol. The residue was crystallised from amyl alcohol in small needles, m.p. 261° (decomp.). (Found : N, 16'89. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 17'11 per cent).

o-5-Aminoquinolinoacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (I, R = C_6H_4N).
—*p*-*o*-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonamide (3 g.) and 5-aminoquinoline (1'5 g.) were suspended in amyl alcohol and the mixture refluxed at 140° for 6 hours. The separated hydrochloride of the product was collected, washed with a little water and then crystallised from 98% alcohol, m.p. 236°. (Found : N, 13'46. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_4S$, HCl requires N, 13'81 per cent).

Condensation of p-o-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonyl Chloride with Aniline (II, R = NHC_6H_5).—A solution of *p*-*o*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl chloride (1 mol., 2'7 g.) and freshly distilled aniline (4 mol., 3'7 g.) in chloroform (40 c.c.) was refluxed on steam-bath for 7 hours. Chloroform was filtered off and the residue washed several times with fresh chloroform. The solvent was recovered from the combined filtrate and the washings and the residue was first washed with hot water and then with 90% methyl alcohol and finally crystallised from 98% alcohol in small needles, m.p. 202°. (Found : N, 10'99 ; S, 8'8. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11'02 ; S, 8'4 per cent).

Condensation of p-o-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonyl Chloride with Diethylamine (II, R = Et_2N).—After distilling off the chloroform from the combined filtrates, the residue was extracted with ether, and the residue from ether was crystallised from 50% alcohol, m.p. 77°. (Found : N, 12'41. $C_{18}H_{21}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12'31 per cent).

Condensation of p-o-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonyl Chloride with o-Toluidine (II, R = MeC_6H_4NH).—The residue from chloroform was extracted with hot benzene and crystallised from 70% alcohol in plates, m.p. 170°. (Found : N, 10'18. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 10'26 per cent).

Condensation of p-Chloroacetylaminobenzenesulphonyl Chloride with m-Toluidine (II, R=Me·C₆H₄NH).—The residue from the chloroform filtrate was triturated with ether. The insoluble residue was lixiviated with water and filtered. The insoluble portion was repeatedly crystallised from 70% alcohol when it had m.p. 188° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10'22. C₂₂H₂₂O₃N₂S requires N, 10'26 per cent).

Condensation with p-Toluidine.—The residue from the chloroform filtrate was triturated with 90% alcohol and filtered. The residual solids were then washed with boiling 98% alcohol and then crystallised from dioxan, m.p. 296°. (Found: N, 9'88. C₂₂H₂₂O₃N₂S requires N, 10'26 per cent).

Condensation with p-Anisidine (II, R=OMe·C₆H₄NH).—A solution of *o*-chloroacetyl-amino-*p*-benzenesulphonyl chloride (1 mol., 2·7 g.) and *p*-anisidine (4 mol., 4·9 g.) in dry benzene (100 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 hours. It was filtered hot, when on cooling a crystalline product separated out which was collected and fractionally crystallised from benzene. The first crop which came out as fine needles had m.p. 185°. (Found: N, 9'62. C₂₂H₂₂O₃N₂S requires N, 9'52 per cent).

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